

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE CHATGPT AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF SS II MARKETING STUDENTS IN MKPAT ENIN LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the influence of artificial intelligence chatGPT on academic performance of SSII Marketing students in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area. Two research questions as well as two null hypotheses were raised to guide the study. The study adopted quasi-experimental pre-test-post-test non-randomized control group design. The population of the study consisted of all 3,724 SSII students in public secondary schools in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area. The sample of the study is 200 SSS II students selected through a purposive sampling technique. Economic Achievement Test (EAT) was developed and used as instrument for data collection. The instrument was face validated and subjected to reliability test. A reliability coefficient index of 0.82 was obtained through split half method. Mean and standard deviation was used in answering research questions, while independent t-test statistics was used in testing the hypotheses at .05 significance level. The result showed that there is a significant effect of ChatGPT on academic performance of SSII Marketing students in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area. The result also revealed that there is no significant effect of ChatGPT on academic performance of male and female SSII Marketing students in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among others that, the Akwa Ibom State Secondary Education Board should integrate AI technologies like ChatGPT into the mainstream curriculum for teachers and students use.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence, ChatGPT, Academic Performance, Marketing*

INTRODUCTION

Since the middle of 20th century, the concept of Artificial intelligence (AI) has evolved at an unprecedented pace, transforming from theoretical concepts to major technological tools for learning. Artificial Intelligence (AI) is rooted in digital computers and computer sciences which describes an attempt to make machines use language, form abstractions and concepts, solve kinds of problems reserved for humans, and improve themselves (Weng, et al, 2024). According to Reuben and Kabilan (2024) education is just one industry that AI is transforming and it is reported that AI will play a significant role in personalized learning by 2025, potentially having an impact on more than 200 million students globally (McKinsey and Company, 2020). The delivery and reception of education stand to significantly improve with the incorporation of AI into educational institutions. Smith and Anderson (2019) averred that automated administrative activities can free up critical time for educators to focus on teaching and mentoring, personalized learning experiences catered to each student's needs can improve comprehension and engagement. Furthermore, Reuben and Kabilan (2024) noted that deeper insights into student performance and learning patterns can be obtained through enhanced data analytics powered by AI, facilitating more intelligent decision-making and intervention.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) refers to machines' ability to perform tasks typically requiring human intelligence, such as understanding natural language, recognizing patterns, and learning from experience (Mondal, 2020). According to Rodrigo (2023), artificial intelligence (AI) is a branch of research in which computer systems are created to execute skills that are often associated with human beings. Artificial intelligence (AI) refers to the creation of machines capable that are capable of doing activities that would normally need the human intellect and intelligence. This includes a wide range of functions, such as comprehending the natural language, recognizing the patterns, and making judgements and decisions, which are accomplished by using a variety of ways, including rule-based systems, expert systems, and more sophisticated methods such as

machine learning and deep learning. In the educational area, AI technologies may significantly improve the learning and teaching processes. (Järvelä et al., 2023). In his opinion, Verma (2018) argued that the study of intelligent machines and software capable of reasoning, learning, knowledge acquisition, communication, manipulation, and perception defines the realm of Artificial Intelligence. In the same way, Ocana et al., (2019) averred that AI focuses on designing intelligent systems that emulate human behaviours associated with reasoning, language processing, perception, vision recognition, and spatial processing.

In today's digital age, the importance of AI technology in students' educational aspects of engagement and outcomes cannot be underestimated. Robert, Potter and Frank (2024) are of the opinion that AI technologies, such as machine learning, natural language processing, and data analytics, are being leveraged to develop innovative educational tools and platforms that can enhance the way students learn, engage, and succeed in their educational pursuits. The authors further argued that with the integration of AI, education can become more personalized and adaptive, catering to the unique requirements of each student. AI-powered educational platforms have the ability to collect and analyze vast amounts of data, enabling them to gain insights into students' strengths, weaknesses, and learning preferences. This data-driven approach allows for the delivery of customized content, recommendations, and feedback, providing students with a tailored learning experience that maximizes their potential for success (Robert, et al, 2024). Robert, et al (2024) further posited that AI has the ability to provide immediate and constructive feedback to students. With AI-powered automated grading systems, students can receive timely feedback on their work, enabling them to understand their mistakes, make corrections, and improve their learning outcomes. This real-time feedback fosters a sense of self-reflection and empowers students to take an active role in their own learning process. Moreover, AI has the potential to facilitate collaborative learning environments. Intelligent tutoring systems and

virtual learning assistants can support students in group discussions, provide guidance, and encourage collaboration.

ChatGPT is a large language model developed by OpenAI that can generate human-like responses to natural language queries. It is a type of artificial intelligence that uses deep learning algorithms to analyze and understand natural language input and generate a relevant and contextually appropriate response. As a conversational agent, ChatGPT is an assistive technology that can be used in various contexts, such as customer service, chatGPTs, and conversational agents. According to Rudolph, et al, (2023) this assistive technology has become popular in education due to its capacity to enhance learning experience of students. Accordingly, Sharma, Kawachi, and Bozkurt (2020) reported that conversational AI have tremendous advantage to the teaching and learning processes. The authors further found that AI-based conversational agents have demonstrated multiple benefits for digital interventions to deliver cost-efficient, scalable, and personalized learning support solutions that can be delivered at any time and any place via web-based or mobile apps. Dai, et al (2023) also found that conversational AI such as ChatGPT have become a student-driven technology with the potential for innovating teaching, learning, and assessment practices in higher education.

Badamasi and Chinonso (2024) investigated the impact of AI-Powered Personalized Learning Platforms on the Academic Achievement and Motivation of Computer Science senior secondary school students in Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC) FCT-Abuja, Nigeria. The study raised two research questions and two corresponding hypotheses which were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted a mixed research method; of both the quasi-experimental design and descriptive survey research design. The population of the study comprised all the public senior secondary school students in Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC), Federal Capital Territory (FCT). A sample of 100 students was selected through a combination of purposive and simple random sampling

techniques for the study. The researchers adopted Code.org as a treatment instrument while the instrument for data collection was a researchers' designed Computer Achievement Test (CAT) and Motivation Based Questionnaire (MBQ). A draft of the questionnaire was validated through expert judgment involving three lecturers. This was done to establish the face and construct validity.

The reliability of the instrument was established through a test-retest method. A reliability co-efficient of 0.85 and 0.80 was established for both instruments (CAT & MBQ). The data collected were analysed by using independent t-test statistics to test the two formulated hypotheses. The results indicated that Code.org significantly improved the academic achievement of secondary school students compared to traditional learning methods. Furthermore, Code.org positively impacted the motivation of secondary school students. The study recommended amongst others that schools should adopt AI-powered personalized learning platforms such as Code.org for teaching and learning. Henkel, et al., (2024) investigated the effectiveness of an AI-powered conversational math tutor called "Rori" on the mathematics achievement of students in grades 3 to 9 across 11 schools in Ghana. The study adopted a quasi-experimental design where students in the treatment group used the Rori tutor for two 30-minute sessions per week in addition to regular instruction, while the control group received only the regular instruction. The sample consisted of approximately 1,000 students, and data were collected using standardized math achievement growth scores. Analysis of the data revealed that the treatment group showed significantly higher math growth scores compared to the control group, with a moderate effect size of 0.37 and high statistical significance ($p < 0.001$). The study concluded that chat-based AI tutoring delivered via simple mobile platforms can serve as a cost-effective and scalable method for improving mathematics achievement in low- and middle-income countries.

Baillifard et al., (2023) examined the integration of a personal AI tutor app grounded in learning science principles such as personalization,

spaced repetition, and retrieval practice—into a semester-long neuroscience course at UniDistance Suisse. The study employed an experimental design involving 51 psychology students, with the AI tutor generating micro-learning questions using GPT-3 and modeling students' concept mastery. Exam grades were used as the primary data for evaluating the impact of the AI tutor, and results were compared with those of a parallel course where the AI tutor was not used. Findings revealed that students who engaged with the AI tutor achieved significantly higher grades, with up to a 15-percentile point improvement. Furthermore, the AI's predicted mastery strongly correlated with exam performance, demonstrating its validity as an effective learning tool. The authors recommended the adoption of AI tutors based on learning science to enhance academic performance in higher education settings. Salman and Chaya (2024) investigated the influence of artificial intelligence (AI) technology on student engagement and the academic achievement, as well as crucial elements affecting learning outcomes. A mixed-methods approach was adapted in this study to collect data from 50 students who used the AI-powered platforms, with a focus on engagement levels, class participation, motivation, confidence, academic achievement, and help-seeking behaviors. The Statistical analysis including paired samples t-tests and descriptive statistics was performed using the SPSS software, the study does not find statistically significant increases in these indicators. This shows that present AI applications in the education may not be completely utilizing their potential. The findings highlight that the necessity of well-informed policy frameworks for guiding the ethical, effective, and fair integration of AI in educational settings.

Almasri (2024) conducted a qualitative study on exploring the impact of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning of science: a systematic review of empirical research. The study offered a consolidated analysis of AI's impact on students' learning outcomes, contexts of its adoption, students' and teachers' perceptions about its use, and the challenges of its use within science education. The study followed the PRISMA guidelines to review empirical papers

published from 2014 to 2023. In total, 74 papers were used for the study. The results revealed that AI-powered tools are integrated into science education to achieve various pedagogical benefits, including enhancing the learning environment, creating quizzes, assessing students' work, and predicting their academic performance. Slimi (2023) conducted a study on the influence of AI on higher education, investigate its impact on the teaching and learning process, examine its effect on assessment and grading, and predict its influence on graduates' future careers. To accomplish this, the study employs a qualitative approach based on a survey of the higher education audience. The results of this study demonstrate the crucial role of AI in the future of higher education. The findings highlight the effectiveness and efficiency of AI in equipping graduates with new skills for their future careers. They also emphasise the importance of considering the ethical implications of AI. The study reveals that higher education institutions need to integrate AI more extensively in their programs to prepare graduates for the future workforce. AI has the potential to revolutionize education by personalizing teaching methods to suit individual student needs, providing prompt feedback, and automating administrative tasks. It can also assist in grading and assessment, freeing educators to focus on developing curriculum and providing quality instruction. The study findings suggest that AI has a positive impact on the learning experience by facilitating the acquisition of new knowledge and skills. This research provides insights into the potential of AI to transform higher education and contribute to the development of new skills for graduates. It has important implications for educators, policy-makers, and other stakeholders in the higher education sector. The study findings suggest that AI should be more extensively integrated into higher education curricula, and that institutions need to consider the ethical implications of AI in the development and implementation of their programs.

Olatunde-Aiyedun (2024) investigated the Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education: integration of AI into science education curriculum in Nigerian universities. Employing a mixed-methods approach, the

research explores the impact of AI integration on learning outcomes, student engagement, and overall educational quality in science education. Quantitative analysis focuses on academic records, assessing the performance metrics of 180 science education students enrolled in AI-integrated courses across three Nigerian universities. Diverse representation across institutions and academic levels ensures comprehensive insights. Qualitative data, gathered through semi-structured interviews with three experienced lecturers, delves into their perspectives on AI integration in science education. Interviews, conducted via online platforms, highlight the rationale for integrating AI into the curriculum and the lecturers' experiences with AI in their classrooms. Statistical analysis of quantitative data, including regression analysis, identifies patterns and correlations in student performance. Qualitative data undergoes thematic analysis, revealing key insights and recurring themes within educators' and students' narratives. The results revealed that there was a positive correlation between AI integration and increased student engagement. It also revealed that AI serves as a catalyst for improved academic performance.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The rapid advancement of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education has introduced new opportunities for improving teaching and learning processes. One of the most notable innovations is ChatGPT, an AI-driven language model that provides instant responses, explanations, and guidance to learners. In recent years, many secondary school students, including those in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area, have begun to rely on ChatGPT for academic assistance in subjects such as Marketing. While this tool promises to enhance understanding, stimulate independent learning, and provide supplementary explanations beyond the classroom, concerns have emerged about its actual influence on students' academic performance. Marketing, being a subject that requires both analytical and interpretative skills, demands that students develop critical thinking and problem-solving abilities. However, there is a growing worry that overreliance on ChatGPT might promote shallow

learning, reduce originality, and hinder the development of these vital skills. Furthermore, in the Nigerian educational context where digital literacy and access to internet facilities vary significantly, the impact of ChatGPT may not be uniform among students. Some students may benefit from enhanced comprehension and improved performance, while others may misuse the tool or lack the necessary digital competence to use it effectively.

Despite the increasing use of ChatGPT among SSII students, limited empirical evidence exists on whether its application translates into measurable academic gains in Marketing within Mkpato Enin Local Government Area. This gap raises the need to investigate the extent to which ChatGPT influences students' academic performance. Without such an inquiry, educators, parents, and policymakers may not have a clear understanding of whether AI tools like ChatGPT serve as a complement to effective learning or as a potential distraction. It is against this backdrop that this study seeks to examine the influence of ChatGPT on the academic performance of SSII Marketing students in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to determine the effect of ChatGPT on academic performance of SSII Marketing students in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area. Specifically, the study examined:

- i) The effect of ChatGPT on academic performance of SSII Marketing students in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area
- ii) The effect of ChatGPT on the academic performance of male and female SSII Marketing students in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area

Research Questions

Two research questions are raised to guide the study

- i) What is the effect of ChatGPT on academic performance of SSII Marketing students in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area?
- ii) What is the effect of ChatGPT on the academic performance of male and female SSII Marketing students in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses are formulated for the study and were tested at .05 level of significance

- i) There is no significant effect of ChatGPT on academic performance of SSII Marketing students in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area.
- ii) There is no significant effect of ChatGPT on the academic performance of male and female SSII Marketing students in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area.

Research Method

The study adopted quasi- experimental pre-test-post-test non-randomized control group design. This design is highly necessary for the study because it deals with treatment of the experimental group to find out the effect of treatment. Two intact classes were used for both the experimental and control groups to determine the effect of ChatGPT on academic performance of SSII Marketing students. The population of the study consisted of all 3,724 SSII students in public secondary schools in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area. The sample of the study is 200 SSS II students selected through a purposive sampling technique. Economic Achievement Test (EAT) was developed and used as instrument for data collection. The instrument was face validated and subjected to reliability test. A reliability coefficient index of 0.82 was obtained through split half method. Mean and standard deviation was used in answering research questions, while independent t-test statistics was used in testing the hypotheses at .05 significance level.

Results

Research Question One: What is the effect of ChatGPT on academic performance of SSII Marketing students in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area?

Hypothesis One: There is no significant effect of ChatGPT on academic performance of SSII Marketing students in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area.

Table 1: Mean, Standard deviation and t-test analysis of effect of ChatGPT on academic performance of SSII Marketing students in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area

Group	n	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference	t-crit.	Df	t-cal.	Remarks
Students expose to ChatGPT	100	7.19	.77	3.38	1.96	198	7.28	Significant
Students not expose to ChatGPT	100	3.83	.91					

The analysis in Table 1 shows that students that are exposed to ChatGPT recorded a mean achievement score of 7.19 and standard deviation of .77 while students not exposed to ChatGPT recorded mean achievement score of 3.83 and a standard deviation of .91. The analysis also reveals that the mean difference of 3.38 is greater than the criterion mean score of 2.5. This implies that SSII students exposed to ChatGPT perform better in marketing than their counterpart that are not exposed to ChatGPT. That, ChatGPT has a positive effect on academic performance of SSII Marketing students in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area. The corresponding test of hypothesis one reveals the t-value of 7.28 and a t-critical of 1.96 at 0.5 level of significance with 199 degrees of freedom. Since the calculated t-value of 7.28 is greater than the table value of 1.96, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is a significant

effect of ChatGPT on academic performance of SSII Marketing students in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area.

Research question Two

What is the effect of ChatGPT on the academic performance of male and female SSII Marketing students in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area?

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant effect of ChatGPT on academic performance of male and female SSII Marketing students in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area

Table 2: Mean, Standard deviation and t-test analysis of effect of ChatGPT on academic performance of male and female SSII Marketing students in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area

Groups	n	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-crit.	df	t-cal.	decision
Female	96	3.71	.79	1.96	198	1.94	Retain H ₀
Male	104	4.93	.76				

Significant at .05 level

The analysis in Table 2 shows that male students that are exposed to ChatGPT recorded academic achievement mean score of 4.93 and standard deviation of .76 while female students that are exposed to ChatGPT recorded academic achievement mean score of 3.71 and a standard deviation of .76. The analysis also reveals that the mean difference of 1.22 is less than the criterion mean score of 2.5, which implies that male and female SSII Marketing students do not differ in their academic performance when exposed to ChatGPT in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area. The corresponding test of hypothesis revealed the t-value of 1.94 and a t-critical of 1.96 at 0.5 level of significance with 199 degrees of freedom. Since the calculated t-value of 1.94 is less than the table value of 1.96 the null hypothesis is retained. This implies that there is no significant effect of ChatGPT

on academic performance of male and female SSII Marketing students in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of the ChatGPT has a positive effect on academic performance of SSII Marketing students in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area. The test of corresponding hypothesis revealed that there is a significant effect of ChatGPT on academic performance of SSII Marketing students in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area. This finding is possible because ChatGPT can moderate students learning experiences by improving personalized learning and active engagement with instructional resources. This finding aligns with Salman and Chaya (2024) whose findings revealed that students who used the AI-powered platforms, improved their engagement levels, class participation, motivation, confidence, academic achievement, and help-seeking behaviours. The finding of the study is also supported by Robert, et al (2023) whose findings showed that with AI powered technologies, students can engage in interactive activities, simulations, and problem-solving exercises, promoting critical thinking, creativity, and teamwork.

The findings of the study also revealed that male and female SSII Marketing students do not differ in their academic performance when exposed to ChatGPT in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area. The test of corresponding hypothesis 2 revealed that there is no significant effect of ChatGPT on academic performance of male and female SSII Marketing students in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area. This finding can be explained by the fact that male and female SSII marketing students possess equal digital competence to engage with ChatGPT. The finding of the study aligns with Akpan and Nkan (2022) whose findings revealed that ChatGPT has no significant influence on gender variation in academic performance and learning competence.

CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concluded that ChatGPT is AI technologies that contribute to academic performance of Marketing students in Mkpāt Enin Local Government Area. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that:

- i) Akwa Ibom State Secondary Education Board should integrate AI technologies like ChatGPT into the mainstream curriculum for teachers and students use.
- ii) Marketing teachers should encourage students irrespective of their gender on the ethical use of ChatGPT to strengthen their learning skills.

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